

Research

SCM as An Effective Tool To Enhance Production And Quality In The Organization

Mohammad Ahsan, Dr. Mohammad Asim, Mr. Salman Manzoor

¹ Karachi University Business School, Pakistan, KUBS, Karachi University, Pakistan, KUBS, Karachi University. Pakistan.

*Corresponding author

Accepted: 05 January, 2020; Online: 15 January, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3609144>

Abstract : SCM mostly is consider by the firm globally, this management mostly interlinks quality management perspective. This competitive global era does not allow the organizations to diverge when it comes to production and quality management. Reviewing an open literature about SCM it can be evaluated that quality and production management problems within and after production firm's SC contexts are essential. SCM can supports a structural and periodic implementation of resolutions for various stages as in product summon back, late delivery of product and many more issues. This paper has address the interlinking bridge between SCM in terms of production and quality. SCM is a procedure of improving business strategies to make them more flexible, rapid and more competitive.

The fundamental purpose that supply chain management exists for is to upgrade the product or maintenance and provide a competitive edge. Successful SCM involves a change in managing individual functions to integrate activities into key points of SC processes, due to which SCM expected to draw out a significant role in organization's role play. The primary reason of this study is to study and examine the main specks that influence the organization in terms of production and quality, and also considering the tools of supply chain management to enhance this productivity and quality for the organization.

Keywords: Supply chain management, structure of SCM, production performance, product quality

1. Introduction

In present competing global market scenario SCM considers a significantly compelling and demands for genuine research consideration, as firms are challenged along to derive out specific paths to meet the rising consumer demands keeping the cost manageable in terms of the

organizational layouts. In doing so organizations should explore the important components of SC procedures aren't vying, determine what consumer wants aren't satisfied, set up developing targets and quickly utilize needed tools for betterment. From history it can be learned that the Great Alexander established his approaches and operations accordingly to his army's exclusive abilities and this was made an effective strategy considering thoughtful SCM planning. His approaches and strategies are nearly fixed with his capability to obtain supplies and initiate a perfect plan that can be considered as efficient firm strategy. If we look further in history Napoleon stated that, "An army marches on its stomach." Napoleon was considered best at planning and a proficient head and this statement helps to learn the significance of what can be said now a competent supply chain plan. SC term was firstly generated around early of times to elaborate dimension and routines regulate by a firm and manage and get hold of supplies. SC enlightens organization and business routines necessary to draw out, develop, distribute, and adopt a product or assistance. Organizational strategies are based on their SC procedures to provide them with which is necessary to grow and exist in the competitive market. All business activities fits into one or more SC processes and has a responsibility toper form among them..

Figure 1: SCM structure

In start supply chain refers to an in-house strategy focus bonded by one firm and how they commenced and get hold of supplies handled by in-house stock and placed equipment onto their consumers. A SC process requires of every level compiled, in all ways for completing a consumer demand. SC process also has the warehouses or retailers, but also the transportation, manufacturer, suppliers and customers itself. The quality or production definitions learned describes that quality is good condition of usage, its value of goods and assistance as given to the supplier, production unit and consumer. The measurement also apply to the degree to which products and services comply with specs, requirements and norm at an adequate cost. Quality is complying with the necessities of the decisive production of the quality that the market requires to be delivered. With all of this explanation of quality and production management in SC procedures can be elaborated

as compliance to requirements. So it can be stated that quality Therefore, it can be analyzed that quality wants from supplier's perspective can be an appropriate, meaningful path of routines and resources to developers so maximum gains in conditions of gains and high rating from developers can be accomplished from optimum available time.

Figure 2: Factors influencing the SC system

SC procedures handles with change overs of raw material into finalized stuff and periodic deliver the products to satisfy customers. This research firstly elaborates definition and growth of SCM, furthermore this research focuses onto derive and indicate the quality and production enhancing tools that generate maximum efficiency for any organization in this global competitive era. SCM essentially sees into correlation, correlated linkages among different objectives, procedures and chain groups which then see forth the effect of inter play on value added and gain maximization. SCM procedures is developed up of various groups for example retailer, manufacturer, and supplier link with the process to provide goods and services for the consumers, singular reason is to the added value to products, both in strenuous and afterwards, by some paths with the correct flow of details and resources available. In this fast paced global business village, it is compulsory to have correct flow of details in the external grid which can be completely leverage by organizational strategic assimilation. This organizational strategic assimilation can provide in collaborating among various groups to accomplish desired conclusions. Various firms started to recognize that now challenging competition rises among SC pathway rather than single organizations.

2. Concept of SCM

In the start of this research there is a necessity to make a small argument on statements of SCM itself. Supply chain management has elaborated by many researchers. Focusing on identical recent research of SC reviews, it's not alarming that there is argument as to be particular about SCM. Supply chain management as a structure of facilities and circulation of choices that leads to objectives of obtainment in terms of materials, changeover of the related materials into transitional and finished products, also the circulation of the finished products to consumers. SCM has integration objectives taking place among a path of available resources that get hold of raw material, change them into transitional goods and then finished goods and delivery of goods to buyers by a delivery system. The SC as the structure of firms that relate, by crucial and most recent bondages, in various procedures and actions that develops significance in form of goods and services to buyers. Supply chain management is the "important and systematic collaboration of the traditional work routines objectives and strategies around these business objectives in a exact organization and around businesses in a SC, for reason by generating longer achievement by single organizations and SC as a whole while different of SC actions between various firms allows business and economies of scale, there are many significant problems and complications that are necessary to be solved for complete SCM planning, it is considered to be the main reason of SCM.

3. Objective Of SCM

SCM is significant in its own manner when it comes to an organizational structure. The most necessary speck about supply chain management is to maximize the financial worth and profit margins for the particular organization. This financial worth that is generated is the difference between finished good worth that to the customer price that was incurred during the SC procedures to fulfill the consumer's satisfaction levels. SCM is one of the optimizing approaches for any organization to maintain their stable position in the marketplace.

After having an abundant literature review, the researched objectives of SCM are listed here below:

1. Resolving and rectifying the supplier's queries at all stages.
2. Improving the services provided to the customers in order to achieve customer satisfaction.
3. Decreasing the before and after price of producing inventory.
4. Decreasing the deviation by certain actions like reduction in the variety or standardization.
5. Stabilizing the cost of procurement and operational procedures to the minimum.

6. Controlling the quantity and quality of the finished good.
7. Accomplishing higher efficiency in terms of working labor, site and capital.
8. Periodic and controlled set of plans that follow to be flexible at certain times.
9. SCM procedures should be instantaneous to respond to change.
10. Managing the supply chain risks by handling the cost disruptions occurring in the organization.

4. Literature Review

SCM is considered as the business philosophy that aims to coordinate the dependent actions, people, and resources from the speck of origin and final destination in supply carriers. Supply chain management is a fundamental, important coordination of business objectives, procedures and under takings within supply chain, for determination of betterment of the longer achievement of single firms and supply chain completely. Supply chain management is considered to be a business philosophy that together should consider all the depending activities, supply chain management accomplices, resources on a functional, strategic, and vital level, from the speck of origin to point of consuming in and among supply pathways. While researching about supply chain management as a tool for the organization, it can be considered as the theoretical framework which embodies the procedures, also practical findings for enhancing the knowledge of significance of implementing SCM and its effectiveness on business strategies. SCM develops to increase efficiency by close integration and regulating the in-house functions within the organization and efficiently combining them with outer operations of suppliers and consumers.

Organization must accomplish a comparative higher grade of assimilation to implement supply chain management strategies successfully, which considers integration, strategy and collaboration across firms alongside SC. The global competitive era has created several increasing objectives for manufacturing organizations. Manufacturing firms which do not follow up with the procedures of SCM would merely exist in challenging market and also fail to achieve to provide to their customers. In this global era manufacturing organizations do not only up take competition on cost of the product but also on who would be the first to inaugurate new technological, innovative, high quality products to allow them to be market trend setters and also gaining higher profits. Supply chain management has the ability to facilitate the firm in accomplishing both price and a value advantage. A lot of researchers states that SCM can be key to betterment for performance, but it can learned that very few studies has been carried out to find out the magnitude and effect of SCM

practices on production capability and quality of the product. SCM was most primarily related to just the management of inventory of SC. This approach with time was broadened to incorporate the management of all objectives within a SC. SCM considers managing paths of levels in a SC procedure to increase complete profitability. Therefore, it is clearly stated that SCM considers management of the circulation of products, knowledge and cash reserves strenuous and afterward awareness in SC. SCM also encompasses making verdicts about areas of production unit abilities, for sorting out what products to make, how to make then and finally, ways deliver these goods.

In order to benefit more organizations have attempted to establish and assimilate supply chain management abilities and functions. The procedure of SC which is studied mostly are SC performance, SC coordination, SC integration, SC agility, SC pathway design. Therefore, it has been determined that this area needs profound strategy thinking because this area is too broad it cannot be easily defined or implemented. Supply chain management considers issues such as developing trust and coordination among SC groups, establishing best practices that can expedite SC procedures arrangement and functional integration, completely addressing the newly derived knowledge systems and internet awareness technologies that generates efficiency, functionality, and quality among SC procedures. Doing so practical knowledge for quality management researchers have developed among the last years. Practical research learning has developed and derived practices. Various researches have derived the relation between quality management functions and numerous points of an organization performance. When it comes to the global market competition move from a single organization towards supply channels of multi-national organizations, considers to change over from management of in-house objectives to the managing of outer organizations. Quality handling managers must develop strategies for organizations that practices with those of consumer and suppliers interests. Integrating quality management and SCM would be significantly for upcoming competing eras.

Quality surety in SCM relates to various things of goods and services provided to straighten the SC obtained quality and surety that for quality to obtain the components which can be accepted by firms to confirm the quality required by the customer. SC association for various kinds of products and services such as FMCG, liable goods and services. SCM is the perfect tools for enhancing performance and efficiency in the organizations and having a timely management of all the specks present in-house and external from the organizations. This type of efficient integration derives various points for attaining maximum profit, a stable market position and enhanced growth for the

firm. This relationship among SCM and QM has been studied by many people and it can be derived from their findings that organizational profit margins can be easily enhanced to higher numbers by improved and periodic supply chain procedures.

5. Theories in organizational SCM

There is an evident necessity to understand the concept of supply chain in the expansion and development of an organization. This research provides a fundamental aspect towards the underlying elements of supply chain in recognizing it as a tool to increase the efficiency in any organization.

5.1 Resource-based view (RBV): Resources are considered most significantly important dimension in SCM because it develops the base of the supply chain for any organization. Resource are very scatter and very little to purchase, they develop a competitive advantage for the organization in order to make a stable position in the market against the other competitors. This strategy of gaining a competitive advantage usually means that these approaches are not yet being implemented by the other organizations and help to minimize the price, making use of market resources and minimizing the expected threats against the organization growth. Appropriate distribution of available resources concludes as competitive advantage.

5.2 Knowledge-Based Theory: Supply chain mostly depends on coordination, this keeps the structure of the organization fixed. This coordination basically depends on hierarchy. Before the evolution of the supply chain this hierarchy was not present in the system. The organizations have to depend on knowledge for several actions, this approach facilitates to take quick actions. Mostly supply chain helps to keep the evident knowledge for any organization.

5.3 Agency Theory: The organizational structure base on its available resources and the resource holders that how these resources utilized by them. An agency combination emerges when several entities are appointed to up take tasks and enable them with decision-making. This way develops a complicated path of targets for both ends of performer, generally agent has higher target than that of initial .Agency expenses are acquired to appoint agents in order to sustain an effective and efficient agency relationship.

5.4 Institutional Theory: This theoretical study depends on the extrinsic pressures or strengths for shaping of firms accepted decisions. It stresses on distinct SC procedures to some

organizations. It administers knowledge to the managing staff and employees to understand and elaborate the success of other firms and to implement pertinent possible actions.

5.5 Transaction Cost Analysis: This theory yield a standard strategy to determine the limitations within which an organization should serve effectively and efficiently. This analysis can be pertained to provide stimulus for the organizations to enter into associations with other firms. Organizational cost reduction analysis can ascertain which functions are to be performed within the firm and which actions are to be considered in the outsourcing panel. When an organization is outsourcing any action, this outsourcing strategy partners the firm with its parent firm. This transactional component also rely on the actions of the partner when it finds some opportunity. Long term contracts with the existing partner minimizes the risks. Penalty statements and jointly investments makes the procedure more reliable. This theory is usually used in taking the decisive decision as in to manufacture a product or to outsource this manufacturing. This elaborates cost reduction helps in deciding whether a particular action should be taken in-house (within firm limits) or to be outsourced (outside firm limits).

5.6 The Network Theory: This era is considered as a competitive marketing structure, it makes the performance of an organization relying not only on its direct partners as well as indirect partners. The procedure in which an organization relates with other organization becomes essentially important in this era. The way the organization relates with other organization confirms the pattern of a new resource. When two organizations join together to establish collaborations and to learn from each other tenacity to develop. The network theory provides a brief elaboration of the significance of relation among both firm, the base is on trust or long-term relation by utilizing each other systems and procedures. The relation among two organizations it enhances networking combination by two different kinds of procedures that is exchange procedure as the two organizations exchange knowledge, goods, services, while the other is adapting procedures where the two organization learn and adopt each other procedures such as legal, administrative and logistics. This theory is basically to develop the essential working system within the organization and also continue the systematic procedures of the working within the organization, this increase the efficiency in the organization and also reduces the wastage. SCM systems can flourish in any organization only if they have proficient communications channels that is only lead by trained staff

members. This strategy allows the organization to maximize its profit margins and work in a timely manner to achieve its set targets. A firm that cannot maintain an efficient working system cannot have a stable position in the competitive market, it makes this phenomenon significantly important for any organization.

6. Research Methodology

6.1 Descriptive Analysis Of Survey:

(1) Number of employees:

64 respondents took part in this survey coming from different departments and designations like managers, procurements officers, planning, marketing and sales, project managers, quality assurance officers and production managers.

Figure 3: Number of employees

It can be seen that 9.5% of the respondents don't know the actual number of employees, this can lead to lack of systematic flow of information within the organizations.

(2) Economic Sector:

Figure 4: Economic sector

This survey determines particularly respondents are subsequently related to manufacturing sector having a total numeric of 44.4%, which is significantly associated with supply chain procedures in terms of quality management and production. Transportation and logistics, import and export, service industries having 1.1% each of the economic sector.

(3) Organizational Issues:

Supply chain is involved from the initial stage for any organization considering management of circulation of raw material till finished product. This question from the survey predicts the in house organizational structure considering customers and their orders. The statement decrease in orders from the clients speculate that there can be unacceptable quality of the desired product or delayed delivery of the product, this can concluded from the 42.1% response from the respondents.

Figure 5: Organizational Issues

Decrease in the production order from the headquarter displays 21% by the feedback of the survey that speculate capacity issues from the production lines or a customer demanding for lower costs. No increase in the new clients from the market displays 28.1% response that shows that due to lack of technological advancement the customer does not want to make his product from the selected organization. In terms of organizational behavior the company is focusing only on the loyal customers that are committed with the company.

(4) Production Cost Attributes:

Figure 6: Attributable cost of production

This question for the survey describes that the role play of raw material in total production cost. Contemplating from the responses 42.9% shows that price of raw material plays a significantly logical role in the product cost so this means that, choosing those staunching suppliers that can supply us the cheapest raw material with finest and outstanding quality within minimum lead time.

(5) Government Intervention:

Figure 7: Government Intervention

Government intervention is essential for any industry because policies and welfare perks provides relief and increase profit margins for the organization leading it to achieve a stable and firm position in the market. 50.2% agreed with this opinion that government intervention is necessary for organizational structure, that government provides adequate incentives for the growth and well-being of the industry because economic position of the country depends on the where about of the

export and import of the country. If the exports are maximum then it means that the country economically strong that's why government want to provide relief to those industries who perform an efficient role in exporting their products.

(6) Just-in-Time Program (JIT):

Just in time (JIT) is considered to be a significant methodology when efficient supply chain procedures are taken in hand, this terminology has a sub-structure that is grounded for the manufacturing sector. JIT has a symbolic dominance on the inventory to decrease its cost. It also plays a vital role in making the system more efficient and coherent by lowering the waste and letting the organization to procure the good delivery when the firm actually need it.

Figure 8: JIT Program

According to the survey majority respondents embraced with 83.9% by accepting this JIT efficient methodology because by selecting this profound strategy the organization can get on time delivery of raw material which will smooth the production procedure and also the quality of the raw material will not suffer when we can get the raw material when the firm wants it. This structural strategy can let the organization to prosper to achieve maximum profits and minimize the inventory cost.

(7) Efficient Tool of SCM:

Assimilation of SCM in terms of coordination, measurement and control are the adequate tools to enhance efficiency among the SCM process. Mostly respondents (88.5%) agreed with this terminology. Coordination performs an intrinsic part in supply chain. The organization must have eminent and loyal supplier, who can provide the things on anytime when the firm acquires it and without coordination and communication the organization can have such kind of reputable vendors.

Figure 9: Tools of SCM

The measurement is also one the important tools for the supply chain process because the customer always ask for better quality of material that can maximize the productivity of its product along with that the customer needs, product assurance, warranty and minimum cost; without these measurement tools supply chain process cannot be that much advantageous. The main objective of controlling is to lower the cost and improving the quality and flexibility.

(8) Measures to increase productivity:

The increased productivity along with better quality become the main reason to satisfy the customer demands and cause to maximize the profit margin of the organization. Productivity can be escalated by installing advanced equipment, this can be accomplished by periodically upgrading the technological aspects within the organization departments. Production planning is also essential for availing higher productivity and without a proper and descriptive production plan we cannot accomplish the desired production margins along with determined quality, in order to meet on time shipments.

Figure 10: Measures to increase productivity

Accordingly from the obtained feedback it can be analyzed that research and development (R&D) is always required for every new product before it is launched by the systematic procedures. Without conducting R&D of the product we won't be able to minimize the hindrances and the defects which will occur during the aggregated production. Mostly respondents (41.3%) agreed with this terminology. Training promotes perfection in the production process, it improves the skill level of the employees to perform their responsibilities with more integrity. In production training plays a significant role by enhancing the quality standards, survey result speculates that 31.8% agrees with the term that productivity can be increased when the production staff will have the trained and technical skills. Extra movement of goods is a wastage of time, resources and slows down the production numbers. For the smooth production we have to design our layouts systematically so that there should be less motion of the material because extra motion would be the cause of time wastage and even there are more number of chances to damage the product. As per respondents 36.5% agrees that conducting motion study and correcting the fault motion is important for the productivity.

(9a) SCM functionality with automated purchasing:

Enterprise resource planning (ERP) is used to interact with the supplier and it is use to integrate the data and information effectively in order to improve the quality standards and delivery of the material. The survey result approves that ERP system can provide an effective automated purchasing segment.

Figure 11: SCM functions with automated purchasing

(9b) Customer satisfaction:

The customer always wants best quality of product for which the customer is paying and that's why it implies on the organization to satisfy its customer because the customer never compromises on quality and moves towards other competitors. The obtained knowledge for the survey also

agrees with that the firm should frequently measure customer satisfaction in order to meet the customer requirements.

Figure 12: Customer satisfaction

(9c) Reliability of firm:

The profit margin of the firm depends upon the satisfaction of its customers and the customer is satisfied when the customer gets the product according to its requirements and quality. To improve the quality of the product, firm need to procure high quality of raw material.

Figure 13: Firm reliability

Therefore, the organization speculates the reliable and loyal suppliers who can provide efficient quality of raw material within minimum delay time. According to the attained observations it can be concluded that 29% of the respondents agrees with the above elaboration when it comes to customer satisfaction and firm reliability criterion.

(9d) Enhancing product quality:

The organization always stay connected with their supplier and they always have a strong interaction and communication pathway. This communication plays a vital role to elaborate the ground work sketching keeping hand in hand both the production and maintaining the quality of the finished goods and this assists the supplier to get feedback from the organization related to quality of its material.

Figure 14: Enhancing product quality

This description can be approved by the obtained result from the qualitative survey analysis, 30.6% respondents agreed to the above analysis that organization contemplate to enhance the product quality.

(9e) JIT speculates cost reduction:

Just in time strategy is used to reduce the inventory because by this strategy the organization can acquire the goods from the suppliers, just at the time when the organization is about to start its production. When the firm use JIT strategy its inventory gets minimized and also expenses which spend on the inventory get minimize. Mostly 29.5% respondents relates to the above elaboration.

Figure 15: Just-in-time

(9f) Firm's relation with key supplier:

Loyal suppliers are the backbone of the organization that's why firm always choose those supplier who are reputable and honest, deliver the required goods of high quality and minimum price with continuity. Above said description is tally down by 29% of the respondents that signifies that organization key role is to secure delivery, reliability and consistency.

Figure 16: Key supplier and organization

(9g) Organizational criteria towards supplier:

The firm always select the supplier to deliver best quality along with consistency and the supplier whom does not compromise the quality standards and also not taking a risk at its reputable position the market. The survey hence satisfy that 29% considers that the organization selects its vendor on the basis of rival products.

Figure 17: Criteria towards supplier

(9h) Time management by organization:

Time management is the key tool in the production procedures in order to accomplish the desired production targets. If the operations are taking too much time to complete then we have to identify the root cause of it, in order to overcome the time loss in production process the firm need to install advance equipment and machinery, provide training to the workers and to minimize the back and forth movement of the goods. The obtained observation from the survey satisfy the descriptive analysis as per 26.2% respondents agrees to it.

Figure 18: Time management

(9i) Pull production system:

The organization refer the pull strategy and produce only those products of which the organization gets the order from the customers. The order to make strategy is helpful the organization because in this way the organization easily estimate that how much material the organization wants to complete its order. 29% respondents strongly agrees with this criterion.

Figure 19: PPS

7. Recommendations

Organization can save resources and money with effective and efficient supply chain procedures. The SCM process plays an essential part of business management. Disruptions and inefficiencies in SC processes develops hurdles in the SC network. When a firm understands its each part of SCM strategic procedures many issues are resolved and creates the entire process smooth. After the extensive study here are some of the suggestions that can make SCM an effective tool for the enhancement of productivity and quality assurance:

1. Strategic planning develops designing, optimizing and evaluating SC model at the initial level for any business.
2. Demand planning creates forecasting, promotion planning and consensus demand planning. An effective demand management ensures organization is producing the required amount of product to keep the customer satisfaction at maximum.
3. Supply planning can enable outsourcing, distribution planning, supply network planning, and customer, supplier collaboration.
4. Devising a distribution strategy to have an effective framework for the supplier management, it provides a better perspective to reduce goods decay, shorten delivery time.
5. Segregate corporate and SCM strategies.
6. Controlling operational expenses.
7. Creating a modern and technological equipped SC organization.

8. Conclusion

This research provides an extensive view of supply chain procedures to enable efficiency and effective work structures within the organization. SCM can be recognized as an effective tool to increase productivity and provide quality assurance with its diverse terminology of constructing a stable organizational structure. Any organization success depends on its supplier and satisfaction of its customers. A poor performing supply chain process develops low overall reliability and maintain higher inventory increasing the cost and also increasing the expenditure costs. This research helps to increase the understanding of the function and recognition of supply chain procedures. The specific suggestions in this study are developed after the detailed study with the help of extensive theoretical researches and survey conducted to generate actual and logical reasoning to recognize SCM as an efficient and effective tool to increase the productivity and quality in any organization.

Supply chain management is one of the key attractions in the current competitive market scenario. In the competitive market the organization having higher quality standards will only survive in the global market. From this research it can be observed that quality assurance is very poorly considered in this global era. The main focus of this research lies in the criteria of recognizing SCM as tool for increasing the productivity and maintain the customer desired quality, this can only be achieved by the structural supply chain methodological procedures. This leads the organization to prosper and expand towards its desired mission in the future.

REFERENCE

- [1] Ajay Das, Michael Behr, Mark Paella, Anthony Ventry “Towards a theory of linkages between safety and quality” *Journal of Operation Management* 26 (2008) 521–535.
- [2] Alistair Mower and Ray Collins “Consumer behavior and fruit quality: SCM in an emerging industry” *SCM: An International Journal* Volume 5. Number 1. 2000. pp. 45-54.
- [3] Andrew Cox, Chris Lonsdale, Glyn Watson and Joe Sanderson “Managing approximately in power regimes: relationship and performance management in 12 SC cases” *SCM: An International Journal*, Volume 9 • Number 5 • 2004 • pp. 357–371.
- [4] Barbara B. Flynn, Baofeng Huo Xanadu Zhao “The impact of SC integration on performance: A contingency and configuration approach” *Journal of Operation Management* 28 (2010) 58–71.

- [5] Benita M. Beamon and Tonga M. Ware “A process quality model for the analysis, improvement and control of SC systems” *International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management*, Vol. 28 No. 9/10, 1998, pp. 704-715.
- [6] Brian Fynesa, Sean de Burcac, Chris Vossb “The impact of SC relationship quality on quality performance” *Int. Production Economics* 96 (2005) 339–354.
- [7] Chandika Diran, S.C. Lenny Koh, Wickramatillake , A. Gunasekaran Subramaniam Arunachalam “ Measuring performance within the supply chain of a large scale project” *SCM: An International Journal* 12/1 (2007) 52–59.
- [8] Dayna F. Simpson and Damien J. Power “Use supply relationship to develop lean & green suppliers” *SCM: An International Journal*, 10/1 (2005) 60–68.
- [9] Desmond Doran, Nigel Caldwell and Peter Thomas “Examining buyer supplier relationships within a service sector context” *SCM: An International Journal*, 10/4 (2005) 272–277.
- [10] Edmund Prater, Michael Alan Smith and Markus Biehl “International supply chain agility Tradeoffs between flexibility and uncertainty” *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 21 No. 5/6, 2001, pp. 823-839.
- [11] E. Christian and K. Kumar, “ICT-enabled collaboration of dynamic supply webs,” *Int. Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management*, vol. 30:3/4, pp. 268-285, 2002.
- [12] Eng, T. Y. (2004), "The role of e-marketplaces in SCM", *International Marketing Management*, Volume 33, pp. 97-105.
- [13] Feller, A.D .Shank, & Clurman, T. (2006). Value chains versus SC. *BP Trends*, March, pp. 1-7.
- [14] Giunipero.L. & Ketchen Jr.D. (2004), “The intersection of strategic management and SCM”, *Industrial Marketing Management*, 33, pp. 51– 56.
- [15] Hines, T. 2004. *SC strategies: Customer driven and customer focused*. Oxford: Elsevier
- [16] Halldorsson, A., Kutak J. H., Skeat-Larsen, H Nickola T. (2007). Complementary theories to SCM. *SCM An International Journal*, Volume 12 Issue 4, 284-296.
- [17] Johansson, J. and Mattson, L.G. (1987), “Inter-organizational relations in industrial systems: a network approach compared with transaction cost approach”, *Inter-Organizational Studies of Management and Organization*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 34-48
- [18] Ketchen Jr., Hult, G.T.M. (2007), “Bridging organization theory and SCM: The case of best value supply chains”, *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 25, pp. 573 - 580.

- [19] Lee, H.L., 2004, “The triple SC”, Harvard Business Review 83, pp. 102–112
- [20] Lin (2009), “An integrated structure for development of radio frequency identification technology in the logistics and SCM”, Computers & Industrial Engineering, Volume 57, pp. 832–842
- [21] Machowiak, W. (2012). Risk management-unappreciated instrument of SCM strategy. Log Forum, 8(4), pp. 277-285.
- [22] McCormack and Kasper, K. (2002). The extended SC: a statistical study. Benchmarking: An International Journal, 9(2), pp. 133-145.
- [23] Matopoulos, A., M. and Manitou, Vlachopoulou V (2007). A conceptual framework for SC collaboration: empirical evidence from the agriculture food industry. SCM: An International Journal, Vol. 12, Issue 3, pp. 177–186.
- [24] M. Davis and J. Heineken, Operations Management: Integrating Manufacturing and Services, 5, New York: McGraw Hill, 2005.
- [25] Melnyk, Lummus, Sando, R. J., Burns and r Vokurka, J. (2009). Mapping the future of supply chain management: a Delphi study. International Journal of Production Research, 47(16), pp. 4629-4653.
- [26] Parkan, C and Dubey, R. (2009). Recent developments in practice of SCM and logistics In India. Portuguese Journal of Management Studies, 14(1), pp. 71-88.
- [27] Rahman, Z. (2003), “Internet-based SCM: using the Internet to revolutionize your business”, International Jr. of Information Management, Volume 23, pp. 493–505.
- [28] Rexhausen, R.and,Kaiser, D., Pibernik, G .(2012), “Customer-facing SC practices -The impact of demand and distribution management on SC success”, Journal of Operations Management, Volume 30, pp. 269-281
- [29] Sachan, and Datta, S. (2005). Review of SCM and logistics research. International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, 35(9), pp. 664-705.
- [30] Spekman, J. W., R. E., Kamauff Jr & Myhr, N. (1998). An empirical investigation into SCM: a perspective on partnerships. SCM: An International Journal, 3(2), pp. 53-67.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

